

Studies in the Absorption Spectra of Cyanacet Arylamides, Dihydroxyquinolines and their Methylene bis-Derivatives

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Absorption spectra in the ultra-violet region of the substituted amides of cyanacetic acid and their corresponding methylene bis-derivatives as well as of the dihydroxyquinolines and their corresponding 3,3'-methylene bis-derivatives have been studied. In each of these pairs (mono and bis), it is observed that the bis-compounds showed hyperchromic effect by the rise in absorption intensity over each of the mono compounds respectively.

MEHTA *et al.*¹ studied the absorption spectra of acetoacet arylamides, hydroxy quinolines and their methylene bis-derivatives in pairs of mono and bis, whereas in the present study similar mono and bis compounds have been further investigated and the extinction coefficient values E of these compounds and the mean at various wave-lengths in the ultra-violet are shown. In class A compounds of cyanacet series the values of the E ratios for each of the pairs (mono and bis) are shown in Table 1, and those of class B in quinoline series are shown in Table 2. Minima and maxima of these compounds (mono and bis) are shown in Table 3.

The curves of class A compounds on plates I to VI are (1) cyanacet anilide, (2) cyanacet-*p*-chloroanilide, (3) cyanacet-*p*-toluidide, (4) cyanacet-1 : 3 : 4-xylylide, (5) cyanacet- α -naphthylamide and (6) cyanacet- β -naphthylamide, as well as their corresponding methylene bis-derivatives (1' to 6'). (Plates I to VI are not shown).

The curves of class B compounds on plates VII to XII are (1) 2,4-Dihydroxy quinoline, (2) 6-Methyl-2,4-dihydroxyquinoline, (3) 6-Chloro-2,4-dihydroxyquinoline, (4) 6,7-Dimethyl-2,4-dihydroxyquinoline, (5) 2,4-Dihydroxy-benzoquinoline (7 : 8) and (6) 2,4-Dihydroxy-benzoquinoline (5 : 6), as well as their corresponding 3,3'-methylene bis-derivatives (1' to 6'). (Plates VII to XII are not shown).

It has been observed that a definite hyperchromic effect is shown by the rise in the absorption intensity of the bis-compounds. From the results of intensity differences of each pair of compounds from minimum to maximum in the series can, accordingly, be placed in the following order :

Class A cyanacet series : 4' : 4, 6' : 6, 1' : 1, 5' : 5, 3' : 3, 2' : 2 (Plates I to VI).

Class B hydroxy quinoline series : 5' : 5, 6' : 6, 3' : 3, 4' : 4, 2' : 2, 1' : 1 (Plates VII to XII).

In class A series, the bis-compounds has far higher intensity than mono, both having similar slopes. Also in class B series the bis-compounds show similar absorption. Sharp minima and maxima are observed in mono derivatives (1-1'), in which introduction of -CH₃ and -Cl groups (3-3' and 2-2'), where influence of both parts on each other seems to decrease absorption with the result that minima and maxima are lost. In class B the mono and bis-compounds (3-3' and 2-2') show parallel minima and maxima, where increase in absorption intensity has been observed. Thus, all bis-compounds from (1-1') to (6-6') of class A and of class B show higher intensity than that is found in mono derivatives with nearly parallel maxima and minima as seen from Table 3. It has been observed, here, from the trend of extinction coefficient of absorption that the bis-compounds showed hyperchromic effect by the rise in absorption intensity, when compared with those of corresponding mono derivatives. These results are in close conformity with those obtained in the U.V. absorption study¹ of acetoacet arylamides, hydroxyquinolines and their methylene bis-derivatives.

Similar systematic difference would be observed on the comparison of the hyperchromic effect with the corresponding pairs of known compounds, as illustrated on plates IX to XIII in earlier communication¹. The hyperchromic effect seen here from the increased absorption intensity and the trend in the extinction coefficient of absorption bands in the bis-series of compounds, when compared with those of their corresponding mono-derivatives, furnishes an interesting subject for further studies.

Experimental

Cyanacet arylamides have been prepared according to the method of Whiteley² modified by Naik³. 2,4-Dihydroxyquinolines are synthesised by Patel and Mehta⁴. Methylene bis-(cyanacet arylamides) and 3,3'-methylene-bis-(2,4-dihydroxy) quinolines

TABLE 1—EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT OF METHYLENE BIS - (CYANACET ARYLAMIDES) AND OF CYANACET ARYLAMIDES, LOG E

A°	1'	1	2'	2	3'	3	4'	4	5'	5	6'	6
2800	4.30	3.99	—	—	—	3.80	4.74	4.07	—	—	—	—
3000	3.99	2.83	4.16	3.50	—	2.94	3.83	3.74	—	—	—	—
3200	3.87	2.90	3.87	2.95	4.32	2.63	3.81	2.78	4.57	4.26	4.50	3.95
3400	3.60	2.70	3.77	2.74	3.79	2.86	3.76	2.90	4.18	3.15	3.18	3.41
3600	3.38	2.75	3.69	2.53	3.52	2.75	3.49	2.78	4.00	2.96	4.01	3.22
3800	3.08	2.70	3.57	2.33	3.29	2.53	3.15	2.70	3.90	2.82	3.87	3.02
4000	2.97	2.52	3.37	2.33	3.20	2.81	3.00	2.86	3.80	2.79	3.79	2.93

TABLE 2—EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT OF 3,3'-METHYLENE BIS-(2,4-DIHYDROXYQUINOLINES) AND 2,4-DIHYDROXYQUINOLINES LOG E.

A°	1'	1	2'	2	3'	3	4'	4	5'	5	6'	6
2400	5.28	5.08	—	—	5.50	5.31	—	—	—	—	5.74	5.57
2600	4.65	4.58	5.25	5.04	5.40	5.27	5.60	5.47	—	—	5.54	5.33
2800	4.87	4.79	5.29	5.20	5.30	5.19	5.80	5.62	—	—	5.30	5.01
3000	4.82	4.72	5.16	4.92	5.45	5.29	5.50	5.35	—	—	5.10	4.91
3200	5.85	4.62	5.23	5.06	5.40	5.35	5.70	5.43	5.70	5.44	5.23	4.76
3400	4.16	2.70	4.92	4.67	5.70	5.00	5.30	5.11	5.75	5.57	4.92	4.73
3600	3.99	2.59	4.46	3.18	4.00	3.47	4.20	3.33	5.43	5.39	4.80	4.57
3800	4.06	2.42	4.40	2.88	3.99	2.88	4.03	3.33	4.60	4.34	4.40	4.16
4000	3.92	2.42	4.55	2.77	3.90	2.99	3.95	3.33	4.40	4.32	4.50	4.11

TABLE 3—MINIMA AND MAXIMA OF MONO- AND BIS COMPOUNDS AT AVERAGE WAVE-LENGTHS IN COMPOUNDS OF BOTH SERIES

Compounds	Mono	Bis										
	1	1'	2	2'	3	3'	4	4'	5	5'	6	6'
	A°		A°		A°		A°		A°		A°	
<i>Class A</i>												
Minima	2980	2900	3600	3580	3200	3960	3200	3200	—	3880	—	—
	3380	—	3800	—	3580	—	3400	3700	—	—	—	—
	3600	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Maxima	3020	3040	3680	3700	3360	—	3240	3560	—	3960	—	—
	3440	—	3860	—	3600	—	3440	—	—	—	—	—
	3680	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>Class B</i>												
Minima	2600	3620	2600	2600	2720	2700	3000	2600	3300	3300	3000	3100
	2900	—	3000	3000	2940	2940	3600	3000	3820	—	3500	3520
	—	—	3600	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Maxima	2800	3780	2800	2800	2800	2800	2840	2840	3400	3400	3100	3200
	3000	—	3200	3200	3000	3000	3200	3200	—	—	3580	3600
	—	—	3740	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

have been prepared according to the methods of Trivedi and Mehta⁵. All the spectra were taken on Beckmann Spectrometer BU Model and ethyl alcohol has been used as solvent.

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